

Crafting the Immaterial Materiality for Expressive Interfaces & Interactions

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Abstract: As the fields of interaction and service design heavily rely on motion and interaction as their material, there is a substantial need to address the nature of such materiality, and to develop methods and tools to work and communicate with its immateriality. In order to further investigate the nature of the immateriality and how the future tools and methods can help designers to design expressive interfaces and interactions, we propose a 6-hour workshop with design professionals in interaction and service design fields, professionals working in teams, and educators teaching interaction and service design. Our eventual goal is to investigate features of a novel tool to enable designers to more easily explore immaterial material for creativity and effectiveness in their designs, and enable them to seed expressions for emotional and felt-life qualities in interactive products and services. Crafting immaterial materiality effectively will also lead designers to grow better communication channels with other stakeholders for co-creating expressive interfaces and interactions.

Key words: *interaction, expression, tools, methods, and gestures*

1. Problem

Designers are traditionally engaged in a conversation with their material during the design process [6]. An industrial designer, for instance, can continuously experiment with the validity of her design work as she bends the plywood in the workshop, and she can be inspired by the nature of the material while working with it by hand. However, it is difficult for an interaction designer to have this conversation with material and develop a tacit knowledge of her subject matter, due to the nature of motion and interaction being the immaterial materiality [5]. In addition, the increasing complexity of design problems requires more and more teamwork and collaboration among designers and experts from diverse fields. But interaction designers do not have a systematical method or tool to support communication of their ideas with different stakeholders. Designers often find themselves handing off static, annotated, screen designs [3,4], before they have sufficiently refined the ideas to know that this is what they want, but these static means often limit their reflection in action and proper communication within the team. As the fields of interaction and service design transform the design practices and rely on motion and interaction as their material, there is a substantial need to address the nature of such materiality, and develop methods and tools [2] to work and communicate with this immateriality.

2. Background

In support of new tools that would improve designers' conversation with the immaterial material, our team had conducted two participatory design workshops at Carnegie Mellon University. The first workshop focused on the group design process in conceiving new ideas, and the second focused on the communication between designers and programmers in the refinement phase. Our findings indicate that there are three methods of expression (how) and three elements (what) that designers use in their process of sketching with and communicating immaterial materials.

2.1. What of Immaterial Materiality

Designers use context, examples and gesture as the three emergent dimensions while working with immaterial materiality to discover what is possible and desirable in expressive interfaces and interactions.

- Context: Designers' ideas evolve around "context" rather than specifics. This context includes different users and situations, and how the interface will behave accordingly.
- Example: Designers actively use examples through telling anecdotes, and enactments to explore possible future contexts and put themselves in users' shoes. They seem to have certain images in their mind that need to be translated to the outside world. Some of these images are idealistic, waiting to be narrated in 'real-life' conditions; and some others are practical, waiting to be elaborated by using state-of-the-art examples. However, current means of sketching allow them to end up with only one relatively poor version of these imaginations.
- Gesture: Among the three kinds of expressions (visual, verbal, and gestural), gesture is critical for sketching the "context". However, currently the richness of gesture is lost in the final visual deliverable, or it is only translated to limited means of verbal expressions.

2.2. How of Immaterial Materiality

Designers use visual, verbal, and body expressions to sketch and communicate their idea of immaterial material.

- Visual expression: Drawing helps both for shaping and representing a concept. In shaping the visual (look) of the concept, they use visual schema and wire-frames, satisfying enough to communicate their idea. In shaping an interactive behavior, they use certain visual elements such as talking bubbles and arrows to express the motion, input-output, or part-whole relation. While drawing bubbles and arrows, the gesture of drawing also tells a lot about the nature of motion they want to use in their design. This drawing gesture oftentimes means the repetition of certain lines, zigzags recurring on top of the same line. Designers tend to clean up these lines when they present them to the other groups, which take out the behavioral and action qualities from the visual representation. When drawings fall short, designers support their drawings with enactments, verbal and textual explanations. There is no certain order for these ways of exploration and communication; however, they do a lot of textual explanation supporting the drawings, followed by enactments using gestures and verbal explanations intensively.

- Verbal expression: Verbal expression consists of anecdotes from past experiences or an imaginary potential situation, as an effort to contextualize or extend the proposed idea. Contextualizing involves both justifying and communicating the idea, so it works as a tool for the designer to refine and elaborate on certain aspects. Sometimes the participants tried to capture the essence of the interface by the title, and in many cases

when they could not sufficiently deliver their idea by drawing, they made a verbal list or added verbal explanation, for example: "I'm just all about words. I'm explaining everything with words (write text under her drawing)." Another case was when the participant felt like his drawing skill doesn't allow enough expression of his idea, for example, "I'm not an artist. So I'll do my sketch... I want to break this down to textural step."

- **Body expression:** We observed that the participants use different kinds of body expressions. They use gesture to supplement what they could not explain enough by visual or verbal means, for example: "I immediately thought of this giant (gesture) projector." Another case was to illustrate a certain scenario by enactment, for example: "I usually look at the bedspread when I do this...(gesture)". They also used the materials nearby them as props: "layer of plastic (touching the top surface of the table) the text is underneath it (touching the lower surface of the table)" Also it was observed that sometimes their gesture expressed certain motion that they want to deliver, for example: "height of the sheet, how fast... (gesture), " or as in the example of tracing the line of an existing drawing to explain the process and motion of the interface. It seemed like they were not consciously using these gestures, except for the cases when visual or verbal explanation were not sufficient to deliver subtle nuances. In many cases, the gestures rather naturally came out as the participants were immersed into brainstorming and conversation.

3. Purpose & Focus

3.1. Purpose

In order to further investigate how the future tools and methods can help designers to work with the immaterial materiality, we propose a 6-hour workshop with design professionals who are working with immaterial materiality in interaction and service design fields, professionals working in teams, and educators teaching interaction and service design. Our eventual goal is to investigate features of a novel tool to enable designers to more easily explore immaterial material and implement expressive interfaces and interactions. We are projecting to reach a better understanding of the nature and scope of a tool that can support working with the immaterial materiality at the end of this workshop. Since designers are always working in a collaborative environment, we will also touch upon the co-creation aspect of such a tool, which will provide shared representations to support informal critiques and communication among the design team and stakeholders. In the long run, the broader impacts of such a tool will be several: enabling designers to freely explore the immaterial materiality; enhancing creativity that will improve the existing user interfaces; and increasing the quality of interactions through products with more elaborate designs.

3.2. Focus

We will discuss the difficulties of having conversations with immaterial material and communicating the immaterial material, how immaterial materials are used in the design process, and how to develop properties of a potential tool to utilize the use of body expression in sketching immaterial material. The nature of a tool, for instance, can ground different strategies and methods to work with the materiality. In particular, we are projecting to have a better understanding of the interplay of gestures with verbal and visual expressions, regarding inspiration, exploration, and communication aspects. While gesture is relatively less studied in the field, compared to visual and verbal expression, it is particularly critical to work with the immaterial materiality, as it is the basis for motion and interaction. Deploying gestures, designers use props (examples) and define

contexts. In this workshop, we will look at how gesture functions in the design process in relation to examples and context. Our major questions on the theme of gesture include:

- 1) What is the nature of gesture? Can gesture be formalized as a way of sketching, or is it that its value is in the improvisation?
- 2) What are the kinds of gesture? Can we separate gesture for communication and gesture for sketching?
- 3) What are the quality dimensions of gesture? Can emotional and felt-life qualities be conveyed through gestures?
- 4) Could grammatical elements of gesture capture the dimensions designers want to deliver and help them to sketch their ideas?

4. Details of the workshop

We will be using the participatory design [1] approach while structuring the workshop with the lens of *reflection in and on action*. The workshop will have three unfolding stages: Designerly Expressions, Hands-on Immaterial materiality, and Tools/methods for immaterial materiality. We will begin with a warm up exercise where designers will investigate the designerly expressions outside of their practice. Designers will be doing role-play in pairs for the scripts that they will come up with, by defamiliarizing their daily routines. We will provide them three key themes: inspiration, exploration, and communication. Then we will move to the design space and ask them to design interactions for a simple interactive control. Designers will be asked to share and discuss their position papers; participate in two sessions of group design activity; present outcomes from each session; and discuss their design process and the difficulties they faced in the process. At the last phase, we will open a group discussion space for tools or methods for helping designers to design expressive interface and interactions.

5. References

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